

Crystal background and sensitivity for the SABRE South experiment

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Abstract

The SABRE (Sodium iodide with Active Background REjection) experiment aims to detect an annual rate modulation from dark matter interactions in ultra-high purity NaI(Tl) crystals in order to provide a model independent test of the signal observed by DAMA/LIBRA. It is made up of two separate detectors; SABRE South located at the Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory (SUPL), in regional Victoria, Australia, and SABRE North at the Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso (LNGS). SABRE South is designed to disentangle seasonal or site-related effects from the dark matter-like modulated signal.

The experiment can host seven NaI(Tl) crystals, each instrumented with two R11065 PhotoMultiplier Tubes (PMTs) which are encapsulated in cylindrical copper enclosures flushed with nitrogen. These are surrounded by an active scintillator medium which provides both passive and active shielding, additionally outside this is further passive shielding to block external radiation.

To achieve the highest sensitivity possible, SABRE is working to produce NaI(Tl) crystals with extremely low background in the 1-6 keV_{ee} energy region. In this low energy region radioactive contaminants dominate the signals produced in the crystals but also noise introduced by the photomultipliers and readout system can become dominant at lower energies. Significant work has been undertaken to understand and mitigate the background processes that take into account radiation from detector materials, from both intrinsic and cosmogenic activated processes, and to understand the performance of the crystal system.

This proceeding will report on the results on the characterisation of and dedicated studies on understanding and reducing noise associated with the SABRE South crystal PMTs and their electronics. The results of a detailed simulation of the expected background due to radioactive contamination of the detector will be shown. The resulting projected sensitivity is shown with a projected 5σ discovery (4σ exclusion) power within 2.5 years.

1 Introduction

The SABRE South experiment is a model-independent replication of the long standing modulation result observed by the DAMA NaI(Tl) experiments. SABRE South is searching for a DAMA-like signal, of an annual modulation of nuclear recoils in the 1-6 keV_{ee} energy region in ultra-pure NaI(Tl) crystals[1]. The search for the annual modulation signal requires a detailed background model that accurately models the time dependence. Mismodelling of the time dependent background is a potential source of bias with magnitude approximately equal to DAMA signal [2]. The SABRE South experiment will host seven ultra-pure NaI(Tl) crystals, Each crystal is coupled to two 76 mm R11065 PhotoMultiplier Tubes (PMTs). The crystal and PMTs are housed in an enclosure made of oxygen-free high conductivity (OFHC) copper shell and encaps with PTFE and OFHC copper internals. The crystal modules are then immersed in an active veto composed of 12 kl of linear-alkylbenzene liquid scintillator instrumented with 18 oil-proof R5912 photomultipliers which are fully immersed in the scintillator. This detector is primarily designed to tag crystal backgrounds, but will also measure external backgrounds and provides additional shielding. An additional plastic scintillator muon veto system, which is used to tag muon events in the detector, is placed above the crystal array outside the passive shielding.

2 Experimental Background

Figure 1: Simulated background energy distribution in the NaI(Tl) crystals of the SABRE South experiment for the 0-20 keV_{ee} region [1]. This plot shows contributions down to 10⁻³ cpd/kg/keV_{ee}, smaller contributions are not shown.

The SABRE South background was simulated in Geant4 using a detector model based on the engineering design. The intrinsic material radioactivity was based on screening techniques such as HPGe gamma ray spectrometry, accelerator mass spectrometry, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry and direct counting of the NaI(Tl) [1]. Figure 1 shows the total background

energy distribution in the 0-20 keV_{ee} region, and the energy distributions of the major contributing components. The largest source of the background is the radiogenic and cosmogenic radioactivity of the crystal, which are discussed in more detail in Sections 2.1 and 2.2. The contributions from the liquid scintillator, veto vessel, veto PMTs, shielding and external sources each contribute $< 10^{-4}$ cpd/kg/keV_{ee}. This is due to their increased distance from the crystals and the passive shielding provided by the liquid scintillator and layers of shielding. These results are compatible with the SABRE South design goal that $< 10\%$ of experimental background comes from non-crystal sources. The average background in the 1-6 keV_{ee} Region of Interest (RoI) is 0.72 cpd/kg/keV_{ee}, this background will make SABRE the lowest background NaI(Tl) experiment and the first to have a background comparable or lower than DAMA/LIBRA.

To explore the background contribution of PMT noise, a series of measurements are being undertaken as part of the bulk-characterisation process. In addition, an empty crystal module housing two photomultipliers will be operated underground and used to further characterise the electronic background, and to develop advanced classifiers for the photomultiplier background.

2.1 Intrinsic Radiogenic NaI(Tl) Background

To simulate the radiogenic radioactivity of the ultra-low background SABRE NaI(Tl) crystals, the activity of the key contaminants was based on measurements made by direct counting at LNGS and ICP-MS measurements of SABRE NaI(Tl) crystals [3]. The simulated energy spectrum of the radiogenic background is shown in Figure 2a. The contribution in the 1-6 keV_{ee} region of interest is 0.52 cpd/kg/keV_{ee}. This is dominated by out of equilibrium ²¹⁰Pb and a conservative ICP-MS limit for ⁸⁷Rb. Both of these radionuclides make flat contributions in the 1-20 keV_{ee} region. The only significant peaked contribution is from ⁴⁰K, which is reduced due to the low concentration in the Astrograde NaI powder and is also effectively suppressed by the active veto system. The actual concentration of ⁸⁷Rb in the Astrograde NaI powder is expected to be approximately 30 times lower than the limit taken from the ICP-MS measurements used in the simulation [4]. This is based on studies of zone refining where repeated melts of the ingot concentrate impurities in one end, which increases the ⁸⁷Rb to a measurable level. These zone refining studies also show the potential for further reductions in the background of the NaI(Tl) crystals.

2.2 Cosmogenic NaI(Tl) Background

The contribution of the cosmogenic-activated nuclides in the crystal is significant as many of these have half-lives which create a decaying background. The cosmogenic activation was simulated assuming each crystal spent three months on the surface during production and shipping before being placed underground after which there is no further activation. The activation of fourteen isotopes was simulated using ACTIVIA [5]. The ³H concentration was increased to ensure consistency with experimental results and to ensure a conservative background limit. The energy spectrum of the cosmogenic background after six months underground is shown in Figure 2b. The dominant cosmogenic component in the 1-6 keV_{ee} region of interest is ³H, which illustrates the importance of using the higher experimental result for the ³H activation. After six months underground NaI(Tl) cosmogenics contribute 0.16 cpd/kg/keV_{ee} in the RoI.

3 Sensitivity to DAMA Signal

For the nominal 50 kg of NaI(Tl) with a background of 0.72 cpd/kg/keV_{ee} in 1-6 keV_{ee} region of interest. SABRE will have 5σ discovery (4σ exclusion) power to a DAMA-like modulation of 0.0119 cpd/kg/keV_{ee} with 2.5 years of live data. The discovery power strongly depends on

Figure 2: Simulated energy spectrum of the intrinsic radiogenic (a) and cosmogenic (b) background of the SABRE South NaI(Tl) detectors [1].

experimental background. this enables SABRE South with its low background to have significant discovery power in a short time period [6].

Figure 3: The discovery and exclusion power of the SABRE South experiment with 50 kg of NaI(Tl) and a background of 0.72 cpd/kg/keV_{ee} for a DAMA-like signal [1]. Shaded bands indicate 1 σ statistical uncertainty.

4 Conclusion

The background of SABRE South has been modelled with Monte Carlo simulation using values measured from SABRE NaI(Tl) crystals and assuming three months on the surface for growth and transport. The expected background in the 1-6 keV_{ee} RoI is 0.72 cpd/kg/keV_{ee}, which is predominantly due to the NaI(Tl) background ($\sim 95\%$ of total). SABRE South will have a 5σ discovery (4σ exclusion) power within 2.5 years.

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